

Research on Painting Scrolls of the Song Dynasty and Their Impact on Modern Film and Television

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ABSTRACT

In order to explore the artistic value of character modeling in painting and the sublimation of the connotation of modern film and television, this paper takes Song Dynasty painting as the research object. First, the surface of the painting is observed with the help of a microscope, and the type of dye and material are tested, and then the shape and structure of the figure are restored and analyzed through infrared scanning equipment and 3D imaging equipment, so as to explore the cultural connotation. The results show that the Song Dynasty paintings mainly use sand, hematite, lapis lazuli, mica, and pyromanganite as dyes, and the canvases are silk, cowhide, rice paper, and hemp, and the painting cost is relatively high. Through color contrast, modeling structure, thick and thin lines, and geometric shapes, the characters show their inner world, as well as the expressions of the characters. Among them, the main frame mainly frames the figures, and the expressions are gradually refined, which is in line with the principles of modern painting. Angular lines dominate men, while curves dominate women. The posture and center of gravity of the characters also have a significant impact on the shaping of the shape. Therefore, the characters in Song Dynasty paintings have obvious characteristics and rich cultural connotations, which can enrich the content of modern film and television and improve their connotation level.

Keywords: Song Dynasty Painting, Character Modeling, Artistic Value Mining, Modern Film and Television Works, Connotation.

INTRODUCTION

During the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC), the influence of color, line, expression, and structure on the aesthetic concept of society was repeatedly reflected in painting. Confucianism places great emphasis on etiquette and modesty, and such aesthetic concepts can be reflected in the modeling of characters. For example, the figures in Song Dynasty paintings are extremely subtle and restrained, dignified and elegant, which are in line with Confucian aesthetic concepts. At the same time, the figures in these Song Dynasty paintings highlight the characters' beautiful and noble character and moral demeanor. At the same time, it is also clearly influenced by Zen Buddhism. For example, it emphasizes that people should pay attention to inner tranquility and try to have the ability to "detach from the world". Such an aesthetic concept can be reflected in the character modeling, which can be reflected in the smiling eyebrows and serene demeanor. and to be able to manifest otherworldly realms. In addition, the figure modeling in Song Dynasty painting was also influenced by the Taoist philosophy of nature, emphasizing the shape's simplicity and the lines' smoothness. In addition, the figure modeling of Song Dynasty painting also has a certain status in the history of art, and has a far-reaching influence: during the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC), the painting figure modeling played a role in the history of Chinese painting, and continued the tradition since the Tang Dynasty, and at the same time, it also made good innovation and development based on this. The Song Dynasty attached great importance to realism and emotional expression, which greatly influenced later Chinese paintings. Shaping aesthetic perceptions. The figure modeling of Song Dynasty paintings can reflect the time's social aesthetic concept and cultural atmosphere, and has a dignified, elegant and subtle aesthetic pursuit. This aesthetic concept has always influenced the creation of Chinese painting in later generations, and

has become an important part of the aesthetic of traditional Chinese art. It has many inspirations for later artists (Escande, 2022; W. Zou et al., 2024). The lines of the figures in the Song Dynasty paintings are very smooth, and their expressions are vivid, and they have the characteristics of simple and bright characters, which provide precious creative inspiration for the creation of paintings in later generations. Many classical Chinese literati painters, such as Wen Zhengming, were influenced by the artistic characteristics of figure modeling and other aspects of Song Dynasty paintings. At the same time, the content of the figure modeling in Song Dynasty paintings, the aesthetic concepts and artistic styles contained in them also influence modern art (Flores, 2023; X. Zou, 2023). Many famous contemporary painters have borrowed or carried forward the dignified elegance and simplicity of the figures in Song Dynasty paintings in their creations. The Song Dynasty was a peak in the development of literature and art in Chinese history, during the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC). The art of painting has been greatly developed (Guarde-Paz & Kwan-Wai, 2022; Zheng, Yang, Y. Zhou, & Shujuan, 2022), and people can find that the paintings of the Song Dynasty contain many different figures, and the depiction of the characters in the Song Dynasty paintings is unique, and can show the social environment and aesthetics and artistic atmosphere of the time, which have a certain value. Based on this, people need to realize that excavating the artistic value of human figures in Song Dynasty paintings is of great significance and worthy of in-depth discussion. Based on the actual situation, this paper discusses this in detail, and at the same time, this paper also discusses other characteristics of human modeling in Song Dynasty paintings (Hu, 2023; Xu, Li, Lu, & Zhang, 2024), and makes a specific analysis of its sublimation effect on modern film and television works. First of all, this paper reveals the unique charm of image shaping and emotional expression by analyzing the characteristics of human modeling in Song Dynasty paintings, such as the realism and lyricism of their figures. Secondly, this paper analyzes the significance of the enlightenment of the character modeling in Song Dynasty paintings to the character image shaping in modern film and television, including how to portray the characters' inner world better. Finally, this paper summarizes how to draw on the characteristics of character modeling in Song Dynasty paintings to improve the character-shaping ability of modern film and television works, and improve their ability to use the emotional expression and artistic presentation of the characters, so as to present a more profound viewing experience for the audience. In short, the research in this paper can provide a new idea and enlightenment for cross-time and space art communication.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Discussion on the Value of Character Painting in the Song Dynasty

Song Dynasty figure painting was developed on the basis of the Tang and Five Dynasties, with the main purpose of firefighting and inspection. It focuses on the characteristics and vivid analysis of characters, and painters are no longer limited to their appearance, but pay more attention to their spiritual and emotional expression, highlighting cultural connotations. The character modeling of the Song Dynasty not only showcases the style of the time, but also enhances its internal beauty and connotation. In terms of selecting and defining themes, it was influenced by the economy and politics of the time, including not only Daoism, historical storytelling, and customs, but also important historical events (Flores, 2023). It was an expression of people's living conditions and thoughts and emotions at that time. Song Dynasty painting was outstanding in terms of technique and innovation, and focused on multiple expressions such as line drawing, character charm, and biological charm. Therefore, the character modeling in Song Dynasty painting has high artistic value, and its cultural connotation also has a modern enlightening effect, enriching visual elements and aesthetic standards, and contributing to the development of modern painting. At present, research on the description of Song Dynasty painting is paying more attention to the description of its characteristic materials, colors, and connotations, and comparing the history of the entire painting and the origins of characters during the same period to highlight the characteristics of Song Dynasty painting, which is supported by case studies for archaeological excavation and painting analysis.

Comprehensive Value Analysis of Song Dynasty Painting Content

So that character painting not only focuses on form but also on its content. Your overall iconic cultural characteristics highlight its connotation and are very obvious, forming a distinct echo with modern painting art. In the process of describing and analyzing modern painting, attention is paid to the analysis of color, dye, shape, lines and other characteristic features of painting to highlight the modern story plot and content. Therefore, Song Dynasty painting can provide support for the creation of modern painting art in the process of overall painting analysis (Prieto & Bustamante Donas, 2023). At the same time, Song Dynasty painting is also an important content and hot topic in archaeological research. By analyzing representative works of Song Dynasty painting, we can understand the rules of painting at that time, the value and significance of painting, as well as the dyes used in

painting, and provide reference for the analysis of painting achievements in the Song Dynasty in China, The analysis of representative works in archaeological excavations can effectively identify and judge the potential connotations in painting, enhance the level of modern painting, inherit the spirit and culture of Song Dynasty painting, and provide important basis for studying painting in the Tang and Song Dynasties, with modern reference value. At the same time, the analysis of painting during the Tang and Song dynasties can also be compared in the same direction. Through the analysis of representative issues, the characteristics and features of foreign painting during the same period can be understood, providing support for modern art creation in China and the integration of Chinese and foreign art.

METHODOLOGY

In this paper, during the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC), the modelling of the figures in the paintings was analyzed as an example, and the dye and paper materials of the paintings were first observed with a microscope (4K HD, 1~6 times, Shanghai), and the shape and structure of the figures were analyzed with a 3D scanner (2Hz/min, scanning depth of 1~2cm, USA). Finally, through the website, the information on the shape, structure and artistic value of the figures in Song Dynasty paintings was sorted out and classified. The samples are imitation paintings, and the data are online literature. Firstly, the characters in Song Dynasty painting are judged and observed through a microscope to examine their shapes, colors, and overall framework structure. Then, analytical instruments are used to simulate the entire character through 3D restoration and scanning, and a comprehensive judgment of its structure and color shape is made to discover other characteristic structures and cultural connotations, especially the cultural connotations representing the cultural and economic characteristics of the Song Dynasty. Finally, the color disease of the materials is observed through a microscope to summarize the characteristics of Song Dynasty painting and provide guiding opinions and suggestions for combining them with modern cultural art.

RESULT

Painting Dyes and Materials

The dyes and materials in the Qingming Riverside Scene were analyzed, and the results are shown in [Table 1](#).

Table 1. Materials of Dyes and Paper

Content	Ingredient	Surface Layer	Transition Colors
Dye	Cinnabar, Hematite, Lapis Lazuli, Mica, Pyromanganese		Limonite,
Painting Background	Silk, Cowhide, Rice Paper, Hemp	Oxide Film	Realgar, Graphite, Talc

From the contents of [Table 1](#), it can be seen that there are many types of dyes in Song Dynasty paintings, mainly mineral dyes, which will have a certain amount of oxide on the surface of the painting, forming a protective film to avoid fading. In addition, during the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC), paper was not popular on a large scale, so silk, cowhide, and rice paper were used as backgrounds for painting. In the figure modelling of Song Dynasty paintings, one can see the characteristics of both realism and lyricism. It not only attaches importance to the vividness and accuracy of the form, but also pays attention to the expression of emotions and often shows the characters' inner emotions through delicate lines and demeanor. In Song Dynasty paintings, the figures paid more attention to the accuracy of the form, and the painters would highlight the physical characteristics of the figures and the decoration of the costumes through thick ink ingenuity and meticulous depictions. The artist pays attention to capturing various details such as the proportions of the figure's body and the contour line to make the figure more realistic and believable. Secondly, vivid. The figures in Song Dynasty paintings are often extremely vivid, and the painters will make the figures full of vitality through the outline of lines and the rational use of colors. The artists will use simple brushstrokes to show the demeanor and movements of the characters, and make the figures full of vividness and three-dimensionality, as shown in [Figure 1](#).

Boundaries of Color

A Blend of Colors

Figure 1. Dye Boundary Observation

As can be seen from Figure 1, the boundary changes of the dyes are streamlined, and the trend of fusion between different dyes is obvious. During the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC), the painting of human figures also paid great attention to emotional expression. The painters will show the characters' inner world and emotional changes through the delicate outline of the lines and the expression of the character's demeanor. Every subtle look, smile, gesture, etc., can convey a deep and moving emotional message. By expressing the various emotional ups and downs in the characters' inner world, the painter can depict the characters in Song Dynasty paintings in great detail, and let people feel the characters' joys, sorrows, sorrows, and complex emotions. This kind of lyricism will resonate between the work and the audience and enhance the cultural connotation and aesthetic value conveyed by the work. In short, in the depiction of character modeling in Song Dynasty paintings, the combination of realism and lyricism not only pursues the accuracy of form, but also pursues vividness (Y. Huang, Chen, H. Wang, & L. Wang, 2022; Xiyi, 2023), and also attaches importance to the emotional expression of the characters.

The Lines and Structure of Song Dynasty Figures

Comparing the shapes and lines of the figures in the Song Dynasty paintings, it is found that the faces of the figures are round, the clothes are plain, and the colors are single, mainly black and yellow, and the figures are scanned, and the results are shown in Figure 2.

3D Microscope Observation

Simplified Lines

Figure 2. The Silhouette of the Person

Figure 2 shows that sharp edges and corners mainly characterize the silhouettes of the figures in the Song Dynasty to show their inner activities. During the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC), these figures' overall shape and structure were outlined through clear outlines. Moreover, artists attach great importance to capturing the figures' basic proportions and appearance characteristics to make the characters more recognizable in the picture. In addition, the figure modelling in Song Dynasty painting will show the structural relationship between the various parts of the figure's body in the painter's clear outline depiction. This sense of structure will make the figure more three-dimensional and more powerful. Judging from the use of lines in the Song Dynasty paintings, the use of lines is very flexible and changeable, and the use of strong brushwork and ink has a soft and tactful expression.

Depending on the situation and character characteristics, painters can choose more appropriate expressions to express their lines (Q. Kang & Y. Huang, 2023) to make their works more diverse. For example, the painter will accurately depict the relationship between the various parts of the character through smooth line sketching and simultaneously show the character's temperament, posture and emotional state. This kind of line technique will make the work more vivid and artistically appealing. Moreover, from the perspective of the overall effect, the figure modeling in Song Dynasty paintings will bring the overall visual impact because of the clear and smooth lines and contours. In this way, the viewer can feel the atmosphere and emotion conveyed by the work through these precise and clear lines. In addition, the lines of the figures in Song Dynasty paintings have distinctive characteristics, with rough and simple lines reflecting their cultural inheritance and innovation. During the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC), the figures in the paintings had the aesthetic concept of traditional Chinese culture, and the colors reflected the aesthetic taste for color in the Northern Song Dynasty. At the same time, the inner life of the characters is expressed through the contrast of color and dark, as well as the posture of the characters, as shown in Figure 3.

The Pose of the Character

Color Contrast Creates a Three-Dimensional Effect

Figure 3. Three-Dimensional Representation of Figures in Song Dynasty Paintings

From the contour lines in Figure 3, it can be seen that the lines of the figures in Song Dynasty paintings are streamlined, and the lines are complex, but the structure is simple. In terms of setting colors, strong color contrast creates a three-dimensional sense of space, making the characters more vivid. The characters of the Song Dynasty paintings can show realism and lyricism, so the lines are streamlined (T. Kang, Luo, P. Wang, & Tang, 2023; Xing, Qi, Chen, Ding, & Zhang, 2023), and have various characteristics such as elegant and subtle and dignified and elegant, the characters are not only mighty, but also vivid, worthy of modern film and television reference. The figure shape of this Song Dynasty painting has a far-reaching influence on the history of Chinese painting. Its various characteristics can reflect the social style and aesthetic taste of the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC), and greatly enlighten the selection of characters in film and television creation. Comparing the characteristics of the characters in Song Dynasty paintings, it is found that the lines used in the paintings are coarse, but the details are relatively delicate, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Fusion of the Contour Line and the Painted Figure

As can be seen from Figure 4, the contour line has a high degree of structural integration with the entire figure plane, indicating that the whole figure is designed through the contour line, and then gradually forms the picture, so the figure is vivid and has a sense of support. In Song Dynasty paintings, the creation of characters often pays great attention to the expression of emotions and the expression of the inner world, and the painter will show the richness, delicacy and profundity of the inner emotions of the characters through the demeanor and eyes of the characters. Modern film and television's characters often reflect elegance, elegance and dignity. The film and television production team will carefully design some costumes for the characters, and take their hairstyles and makeup seriously (Liu, 2022; S. Wang, 2022), so as to show the aesthetic style of the characters. At the same time, the actors will interpret the characters' inner world and emotional changes through their unique performance skills and emotional control capabilities, making the characters more three-dimensional and vivid. This common pursuit of elegant, dignified and restrained aesthetic values can reflect some people's recognition of noble character and artistic beauty in ancient and modern times. Whether it is the character modeling in Song Dynasty paintings or the characters in modern film and television works, they can reflect the yearning and pursuit of beauty in their aesthetic pursuit. At the same time, it can demonstrate people's general recognition of beauty and artistic value, build a strong bridge between traditional culture and contemporary art, and promote cultural exchange and inheritance.

DISCUSSION

To Enhance the Connotation of Character Performance

In many modern film and television works, the characters are carefully designed, so film and television directors will refer to the clothing and hairstyle design of the characters in Song Dynasty paintings. Then, based

on the reproduction of the Song Dynasty clothing style and hairstyle, to create an aesthetic effect that blends classical and fashion. Modern film and television works will focus on the character's demeanor and expression, and refer to the characters' inner world and emotional expression in Song Dynasty paintings. In addition, modern film and television dramas will also use very delicate facial expressions and acting skills to reproduce the dignified and elegant aesthetic characteristics similar to those expressed in Song Dynasty paintings (Ma et al., 2023). In some film and television works, the presentation of the posture and action of the characters will also refer to the characteristics of the characters in Song Dynasty paintings. For example, the aesthetic pursuit of the figures in Song Dynasty paintings is reproduced through dignified and elegant postures and movements. In terms of the background and environment creation, the film and television works will draw on the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC), and the background environment and the characters in the painting will be used to set off each other. Take advantage of the opportunity to arrange the background in a simple, fresh and elegant way to highlight the characters and create an atmosphere of fashion, classicism, and rich connotations. In some film and television works, people will improve the image of the characters by reproducing the emotional expression of the characters in the Song Dynasty paintings and the deepening of the connotation, so as to make them more layered and artistic (Prieto & Donas, 2023; G. Wang, 2023). Through the in-depth portrayal of the characters' inner world and emotional changes, the characters can become more three-dimensional and vivid. Modern film and television works will draw on the characters in Song Dynasty paintings, for example, from various aspects such as costumes, demeanor, background, etc., to show the essence of traditional Chinese culture and show respect for it. Such quotations and reproductions can enrich the image shaping techniques of film and television works and truly inject vitality into traditional culture and art. In addition, it can also promote the wider dissemination and inheritance of traditional culture in the current society. Modern film and television works can better inherit and promote the excellent traditional Chinese culture by sublimating and innovating the character modelling in Song Dynasty paintings. For example, the artistic style and aesthetic concepts in Song Dynasty paintings can be integrated into modern film and television works, so that the audience can better understand and feel the charm of traditional Chinese culture. Drawing on modeling the characters in Song Dynasty paintings, and making innovations and sublimations based on this, can improve the cultural connotation and artistic value of film and television works to a certain extent. For example, classical aesthetic elements can be integrated into film and television works to make the character image more historical and cultural and add a more unique artistic charm to film and television works. During the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC), the sublimation and innovation of the figure modeling in the painting can change people's concepts and better understand the character image, because, to a certain extent, this can greatly enrich the shaping techniques of the character image, and based on the reference effect brought by the characteristics of classical aesthetics, it can be combined with modern aesthetic tastes to innovate, and make the characters more three-dimensional and vivid, more full of personality characteristics (Shui et al., 2022; Tsai, 2023). One can find that there is an emotionally expressive connection between the two. For example, both attach great importance to the emotional expression of the characters. The painter will reflect the inner emotions of the characters through their demeanor, expressions, postures, etc., and make the characters more three-dimensional and vivid, and at the same time, more emotionally resonant. In Song Dynasty paintings, painters used dexterous brushwork and delicate painting expressions to show the characters' movements, expressions, and demeanour so as to express their inner world and emotional experience. For example, in "The Riverside Scene at Qingming Festival", the characters are very vivid and natural, and each character can show a different and very real emotional state, some are smiling, while others are more comfortable, and some are worried. This kind of emotional expression allows the viewer to enter the background, environment, and life of the characters in the painting. In modern film and television works, people will find that actors will interpret the characters' inner world and emotional changes with their exquisite personal performance skills and characteristics, emotional control ability, etc. It often uses subtle gestures and expressions, appropriate postures, etc., to show the characters' complex emotions, such as joy, anger, sorrow, love and hatred. At the same time, the audience can also form an emotional connection with them through the emotional characteristics they display, generate emotional resonance, and better understand the deep meaning behind the story. In short, in both of them, in fact, they will convey the characters' inner world and emotional state through the characters' demeanor, expressions, postures, etc. In this way, the characters become more vivid and three-dimensional, so the audience can truly understand them and resonate with them.

To Evoke the National Plot in Modern Film and Television Dramas

The character modeling in Song Dynasty paintings and some characters in modern film and television works will have a connection in aesthetic pursuit. For example, they pay attention to beauty and aesthetic value and whether the character image is elegant and dignified. This kind of aesthetic pursuit can highlight the pursuit of beauty and the degree of respect in ancient and modern times, and show its pursuit of art, which has a very profound cultural connotation and has certain historical significance. In the figure modelling in Song Dynasty

paintings, painters used their unique brush and ink techniques and expression techniques to create delicate, dignified, and elegant figures that maintained subtlety. They attach great importance to the smoothness of the lines and the accuracy of the structure, and they like to outline the beauty of the figure through concise brushwork and show their elegance. Inherit and carry forward traditional Chinese culture. In addition, it also increases the depth and breadth of character building. In modern film and television works, the characters in the paintings of the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC) are sublimated and innovated better to display the charm of the excellent traditional Chinese culture and promote the exchange and integration between different cultures. Based on this, more classical aesthetic elements can be integrated into modern film and television works, showing the essence of excellent traditional Chinese culture. Through the sublimation and inheritance of the character modeling in Song Dynasty paintings, the sense of history and cultural heritage can be displayed in modern film and television works, and the aesthetic emotions of the audience can be better stimulated. When appreciating these characters that have been carefully designed, it is necessary to feel a deep aesthetic enjoyment. In short, sublimating and innovating the character modeling of Song Dynasty paintings in modern film and television works can reflect the cultural and artistic value of the Song Dynasty, and form a new collision to achieve the integration of film and television with different themes, and can reflect the unique value of film and television works. In addition, it can also inject more vitality into traditional culture and further promote cultural exchange and development. There are some examples that can better demonstrate the connection between the character modeling in Song Dynasty paintings and the character image in modern film and television works. For example, in the paintings of the Song Dynasty, such as in the "Riverside Scene at Qingming Festival", there are some figure shapes, which can show the dignified and elegant temperament of women at that time. Its figures are often depicted in smooth lines and have a serene demeanor, which can reflect a noble and elegant temperament. In modern film and television works, such as the modern romance costume drama "Three Lives, Three Worlds and Ten Miles of Peach Blossoms", the heroine Bai Qian's character image is very classical, her hairstyle and hair accessories are simple and exudes a unique elegant charm, her character image is full, and her demeanor is dignified and elegant, which can show a unique aesthetic style after the combination of classical and fashion. Based on this, it can be seen that in modern film and television works, people can combine the character modeling in Song Dynasty paintings to improve the character image's beauty, and find each other's aesthetic value, so as to better integrate. The character modeling in Song Dynasty paintings is often very important, and the characters in modern film and television works also have good aesthetic value. The figures in Song Dynasty paintings pay more attention to the background and the mutual foil of the characters, which can make modern film and television works create a more complete and harmonious picture, and improve the overall artistic appeal. In addition, the dignified and elegant aesthetic pursuit will be able to inject a noble and elegant temperament into the character image of modern film and television works, so as to make the connotation of the characters in the work more profound, more aesthetically practicable, and improve the artistic value of the work. Therefore, in shaping the character image, emotional expression, and artistic presentation of modern film and television works, the artistic value of the character modeling in Song Dynasty paintings can play a certain role in sublimation, so that the audience can truly resonate.

Inherit the Skills of Figure Painting in the Song Dynasty

During the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC), the figures were painted very simply and subtly, and they sketched them through concise lines and crisp brushwork. This style is extremely simple, and pays attention to the purity and simplicity of the image, and also likes to express the personal emotions of the characters through very simple lines, showing their temperament. Moreover, the figure modeling in Song Dynasty painting also pays great attention to static expression, for example, it shows the image of the character through some static elements such as the posture and demeanor of the figure. This static expression allows the viewer to immerse themselves in a quiet, quiet and peaceful atmosphere, and experience a sense of inner peace and quiet. In contrast, in modern film and television works, its character image will have these characteristics. For example, in terms of dynamic performance. The portrayal of characters in modern film and television works will pay more attention to dynamic performance, that is, through a series of dynamic elements such as the actions and emotional changes of the characters themselves to show their images. To this end, the actor will interpret the character's inner world and emotional changes through his superb acting skills and special effects to make the character more three-dimensional. In modern film and television works, the characters are also enriched through the unique use of special effects techniques and their three-dimensional surface. To this end, the crew will use various means such as visual effects and sound effects to create a more shocking and fantastical atmosphere for people and make the character image extremely dramatic and impactful. In terms of expression, the figures in Song Dynasty paintings are simpler and subtle, and they pay more attention to static expression. However, the character creation in modern film and television works pays more attention to dynamic presentation and the use of special effects. Such differences can reflect the changes in the creative styles of different art forms in ancient and modern times and the changes in modern aesthetic tastes, and show the diversity and richness of artistic creation in different

historical backgrounds. Secondly, the background environment. From the perspective of the background environment, in the Song Dynasty paintings, the background of the characters will be different from the characters in modern film and television works. In Song Dynasty paintings, the figures are generally modeled with simple backgrounds and focus on the figures themselves. Moreover, its background often includes some simple elements, such as landscape, architectural, decorative, etc., which are relatively simple. Based on this, the image of the character can be set off, and the audience can better pay attention to the character itself, including the character's expression, demeanor, posture, etc. At the same time, in the Song Dynasty paintings, the figure modeling also emphasizes the way of line outline, which is concise and vivid, so that the figure can appear more prominent and vivid in the background. This kind of expression will immerse the audience more in the characters' inner feelings. In comparison, the background layout of the characters in modern film and television works is more complex, and at the same time, they will use these complex backgrounds and special effects to improve the drama and impact of the background environment, and make it more colourful. Moreover, in modern film and television works, there will also be some well-designed background environments, which creators can use to create the atmosphere and emotional tension required by the plot. The complex background arrangement can help the audience better understand the storyline, the relationship between the characters, and the emotions and themes conveyed in the story. In short, in terms of the background environment, the figures in Song Dynasty paintings pay more attention to simplicity and pay great attention to the figures themselves. Moreover, modern film and television works also prefer to create a good atmosphere for people through complex background arrangements and special effects. Such differences can reflect the changes in aesthetic tastes and artistic creation styles in different periods, showing art's diversity and richness in various historical periods. The characters in Song Dynasty paintings are realistic and lyrical, dignified and elegant, elegant and subtle, etc., which can sublimate the character shaping and artistic expression of modern film and television works. The characters in Song Dynasty paintings pay attention to the richness of their inner world and emotional expression, which can make modern film and television works more deeply portray the inner world and emotional changes of the characters, so that the characters become more three-dimensional and have stronger resonance. The figures in Song Dynasty paintings have a very unique artistic style and aesthetic characteristics in terms of the pursuit of vivid charm and the contrast between the background and the characters, lyricism and realism. At that time, painters would outline the characters through simple and bright lines and combine them with delicate expressions to show the charm of the figures. The figures in Song Dynasty paintings can not only show the elegant connotation and noble temperament of the figures but also integrate with the background environment to form a complete and harmonious picture. Such an aesthetic pursuit can reflect the social and cultural outlook and aesthetic taste of the time and provide great inspiration and reference for later generations of artists. At the same time, it has a certain role in the sublimation of the connotation of modern film and television, and it has a certain connection and difference with the character image shaping in modern film and television works.

CONCLUSION

During the Song Dynasty (960~1279 AC), the figures in the paintings had unique artistic value, and in-depth excavation of their artistic characteristics could enrich the archaeological content. And it can sublimate in the connotation of modern film and television. Through the test of microscope, infrared scanner and 3D imaging equipment, it was found that the dyes of Song Dynasty paintings were relatively diverse, and the dyeing effect was better. However, the painting materials of the Song Dynasty were more expensive, mainly silk, silk, linen, etc. In terms of character drawing, attention is paid to the combination of geometric figures, and the majesty of the characters is expressed through the edges and corners, and the actions represent the hearts of the people, and the character display process is more delicate. Although the characters are drawn with rough lines, attention to detail is taken so that the characters are drawn vividly. The characters are designed through the frame and then drawn on a flat surface, so the characters are more three-dimensional. At the same time, through the contrast of colors, the vividness of the characters and the inner activities are enhanced. On the whole, Song Dynasty painting has rich cultural connotations, and the use of lines, colours, and structures is incisive, which can support the development of modern film and television and promote the sublimation of its connotation. There are deficiencies in the research of this paper, mainly because the Song Dynasty paintings are rich in content and the selection of representative cases is incomplete, and we will focus on analysis in the future.

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